

INDUCTIVE AND DEDUCTIVE GRAMMAR TEACHING.

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ABSTRACT

This article contains information about investigation of effectiveness of teaching English by using deductive and inductive approaches of teaching grammar. The investigation also attempts to see which of these two methods has a positive effect on the grammar academic achievement of the higher education, so it answers to the following questions: What are inductive and deductive approaches of teaching grammar? What advantages and disadvantages they have got? What is the effect of inductive method on grammar achievement compared to deductive method at secondary school? · What is the effect of inductive method on grammar achievement compared to deductive method at secondary school? To answer the questions of the study, the researcher has made research based on inductive and deductive methods for each level based on its syllabus.

There are two main ways that we tend to teach grammar: deductively and inductively. Both deductive and inductive teaching have their pros and cons and which approach we use when can depend on a number of factors, such as the nature of the language being taught and the preferences of the teacher and learners. It is, however, perhaps generally accepted that a combination of both approaches is best suited for the EFL classroom.

Deductive and inductive reasoning.

Deductive reasoning is essentially a top-down approach which moves from the more general to the more specific. In other words, we start with a general notion or

theory, which we then narrow down to specific hypotheses, which are then tested. Inductive reasoning is more of a bottom-up approach, moving from the more specific to the more general, in which we make specific observations, detect patterns, formulate hypotheses and draw conclusions.

Deductive:	general	→	specific
Inductive:	specific	→	general

Deductive and inductive grammar learning. These two approaches have been applied to grammar teaching and learning. A deductive approach involves the learners

being given a general rule, which is then applied to specific language examples and honed through practice exercises. An inductive approach involves the learners detecting, or noticing, patterns and working out a 'rule' for themselves before they practise the language.

Both approaches are commonplace in published materials. Some course books may adhere to one approach or the other as series style, whereas some may be more flexible and employ both approaches according to what the language being taught lends itself to. Most inductive learning presented in course books is guided or scaffolded. In other words, exercises and questions guide the learner to work out the grammar rule.

First and foremost, it is perhaps the nature of the language being taught that determines if an inductive approach is possible. Inductive learning is an option for language with salient features and consistency and simplicity of use and form. The basic forms of comparative adjectives, as shown above, is an example of this. Conversely, teaching the finer points of the use of articles (*a/an, the*) inductively, for example, would most probably be problematic. The metalinguistic tools that the learners will need to accomplish the task is also a factor.

However, the learner-centred nature of inductive teaching is often seen as advantageous as the learner is more active in the learning process rather than being a passive recipient. This increased engagement may help the learner to develop deeper understanding and help fix the language being learned. This could also promote the strategy of 'noticing' in the student and enhance learner autonomy and motivation.

On the other hand, inductive learning can be more time- and energy-consuming and more demanding of the teacher and the learner. It is also possible that during the process, the learner may arrive at an incorrect inference or produce an incorrect or incomplete rule. Also, an inductive approach may frustrate learners whose personal learning style and/or past learning experience is more in line with being taught via a more teacher-centred and deductive approach.

Nevertheless, while there are pros and cons to both approaches and while a combination of both inductive and deductive grammar teaching and learning is probably inevitable, an inductive approach does seem to be broadly accepted as being more efficient in the long run, at least for some learners.

In teaching, there are many theoretical approaches that have been developed to promote the students' success in learning new information. In TESOL (Teaching English to Students of Other Languages), there are two main theoretical approaches for the presentation of new English grammar structures or functions to ESL/EFL students: inductive approach and deductive approach. They both have advantages and disadvantages.

The deductive approach represents a more traditional style of teaching in that the grammatical structures or rules are dictated to the students first, a more effective and time saving way under certain circumstances, namely monolingual classes. Thus, the students learn the rule and apply it only after they have been introduced to the rule. For example, if the structure to be presented is present perfect, the teacher would begin the lesson by saying, "Today we are going to learn

how to use the present perfect structure". Then, the rules of the present perfect structure would be outlined and the students would complete exercises, in a number of ways, to practice using the structure. In this approach, the teacher is the center of the class and is responsible for all of the presentation and explanation of the new material.

The inductive approach represents a different style of teaching where the new grammatical structures or rules are presented to the students in a real language context. The students learn the use of the structure through practice of the language in context, and later realize the rules from the practical examples. For example, if the structure to be presented is the comparative form, the teacher would begin the lesson by drawing a figure on the board and saying, "This is Jim. He is tall." Then, the teacher would draw another taller figure next to the first saying, "This is Bill. He is taller than Jim." The teacher would then provide many examples using students and items from the classroom, famous people, or anything within the normal daily life of the students, to create an understanding of the use of the structure. The students repeat after the teacher, after each of the different examples, and eventually practice the structures meaningfully in groups or pairs. With this approach, the teacher role is to provide meaningful contexts to encourage demonstration of the rule, while the students evolve the rules from the examples of its use and continued practice. In both approaches the students practice and apply the use of the grammatical structure, yet, there are advantages and disadvantages to each in the EFL/ESL classroom. The deductive approach can be

effective with students of a lower level, who are beginning to learn the basic structures of the language, or with students who are accustomed to a more traditional style of learning and expect grammatical presentations. The deductive approach however, is less suitable for upper level language students, for presenting grammatical structures that are complex in both form and meaning, and for classrooms that contain younger learners. The advantages of the inductive approach are that students can focus on the use of the language without being held back by grammatical terminology and rules that can inhibit fluency. The inductive approach also promotes increased student participation and practice of the target language in the classroom, in meaningful contexts. The use of the inductive approach has been noted for its success in EFL/ESL classrooms world-wide, but its disadvantage is that it is sometimes difficult for students who expect a more traditional style of teaching to induce the language rules from context and that it is more time consuming. Understanding the disadvantages and advantages of both approaches, may help the teacher to vary and organize the EFL/ESL lesson, in order to keep classes interesting and motivating for the students.

What is inductive and deductive grammar teaching? What are advantages and disadvantages? Which is better? In this article we will look through some principles of using these approaches. Inductive grammar teaching, as Trochim defines, is moving from the specific to the general, while deductive method is moving from general to the specific. If arguments are based on experience or observation, it is best to explain grammar inductively.

When arguments are based on laws, rules, or other widely accepted principles, it is advised to teach grammar deductively. Creswell and Plano Clark say that the deductive researcher “works from the ‘top down’, from a theory to hypotheses to data to add to or contradict the theory”. In contrast, they define the inductive researcher as someone who works from the “bottom-up, using the participants’ views to build broader themes and generate a theory interconnecting the themes”. And in my opinion the ideas of all mentioned scientists have the same meaning.

In some research works these two approaches are also known as quantitative (deductive) and qualitative (inductive) and they have been competing for over the years as Onwuegbuzie and Leech suggest. In quantitative method it is believed that teachers should separate themselves from the learners while qualitative teachers are aware that the relationship between them and their students is important in the understanding of the class. Both approaches are commonplace in published materials. Some course books may have practices on one approach or the other as series style, whereas some may be more flexible and have both practices including both approaches according to what is taught. Most inductive learning presented in course books is guided. In other words, exercises and questions guide the learner to work out the grammar rule. The methods may be different but the goals remain the same and both approaches have advantages and disadvantages.

The advantages of a deductive approach :

-It gets straight to the point, and so can be time-saving. Many rules – especially rules

of form – can be simply and quickly explained and allow more time for practice and application.

-It is very suitable for the intelligence and maturity of many adult students, as well as acknowledges the role of cognitive processes in language acquisition.

-It gives opportunity for the teacher to deal with language points as they come up, rather than having to prepare some materials in advance.

The disadvantages of a deductive grammar approach:

-Starting the lesson with a grammar presentation may be not understandable for some students, especially at young ages. They may not have sufficient language (language which is used to talk about grammar rules). They may not be able to understand the rules involved.

-Grammar explanation encourages a teacher-centered, transmission-style classroom; teacher explanation is often at higher position than students’ involvement and interaction.

-Such an approach encourages the belief that learning a language is simply a case of knowing the rules.

The advantages of an inductive approach:

- Rules learners discover for themselves (student-centered) how to use, when to use some structures than rules they have been presented with. This makes the rules more meaningful, memorable and acquired.

The disadvantages of an inductive approach:

-Much time and energy are spent while working out rules with students.

-The time taken to work out a rule may be at the expense of time spent in putting the rule to some sort of productive practice.

-It can demand teachers to work on planning a lesson. They need to select and organize the data carefully so as to guide learners to an accurate formulation of the

rule, while also ensuring the data is intelligible.

-An inductive approach frustrates students who would prefer simply to be told the rule.

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